

Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from the Perspective of Maqashid Sharia

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the optimization of the role of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in realizing sharia compliance and transparency as an effort to prevent fraud in Sharia Financial Institutions (LKS) from the perspective of maqashid sharia. The research method used a descriptive qualitative approach through literature study and field data obtained from interviews and questionnaires with the DPS, management, and auditors of LKS. The results showed that the DPS plays a strategic role not only as a formal supervisor of sharia compliance but also as a guardian of maqashid values oriented towards benefit and the prevention of harm. The active involvement of the DPS in product development and operational supervision can increase transparency and reduce the potential for fraud. However, the effectiveness of the DPS's role still faces challenges in the form of limited competence, potential conflicts of interest, and weak utilization of surveillance technology. Therefore, strengthening independence, increasing competence, and integrating a digital-based surveillance system are important steps in optimizing the role of the DPS. This study concludes that optimizing the role of the DPS based on sharia maqashid contributes significantly to strengthening governance and preventing fraud in LKS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sharia Financial Institutions (SFIs) are one of the main instruments in promoting economic development that is in line with sharia principles. Islamic financial institutions differ from conventional financial institutions in that IFIs operate with the aim of obtaining financial profits while ensuring that every business activity is in line with Islamic values (Hussain et al., 2022; Kholidah et al., 2025; Moqbel & Ahmed, 2020). LKS not only acts as a development agent oriented towards public welfare. This can be seen from LKS's involvement in supporting small and medium enterprise financing, providing waqf and zakat-based products, to developing environmentally friendly and sustainable financing instruments. The strategic responsibility of Islamic financial institutions has moral and social principles to maintain sharia

integrity in all of their activities (Derbali et al., 2017; Mohamed & Ibrahim, 2024; Suzuki & Miah, 2021).

The Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) within the LKS structure holds a key position as the guardian of sharia compliance. The DPS is tasked with ensuring that all products, services, transactions, and operations of the institution are in accordance with the principles of muamalah established by the Indonesian Sharia Council (Agriyanto, 2015; Hasan et al., 2020; Moqbel & Ahmed, 2020) (Agriyanto, 2015; Hasan et al., 2020; Moqbel & Ahmed, 2020). The functions of the DPS include providing operational opinions and fatwas, reviewing product structures, verifying contracts, conducting routine supervision, and issuing compliance opinions that serve as guarantees for regulators and stakeholders. The DPS also plays a role in maintaining public trust through transparency and integrity, thus becoming an important link between the

“Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from The Perspective of Maqashid Sharia”

institution and the community. The competence of DPS members is crucial in carrying out these functions. Ideally, the DPS should consist of muamalah fiqh experts who understand the principles of modern Islamic finance, have an understanding of risk management and technology, and are committed to independence and professional ethics.

DPS structurally operates within a governance framework that supports effective supervision. This is realized through the concept of *three lines of defense*. In the first line, business units are responsible for conducting operations in accordance with sharia procedures; in the second line, the sharia compliance unit or risk management ensures consistent implementation of these principles; and in the third line, the internal sharia audit s conducts a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of controls and compliance. The DPS is above all three as an independent supervisor that authorizes key policies, monitors implementation in the field, and assesses the effectiveness of controls. The DPS is involved in the development of LKS products from the pre-launch stage, namely by reviewing product ideas, examining contract structures, ensuring there are no elements of usury, gharar, or maisir, and providing written opinions as a basis for product launches. After the product is launched, the DPS monitors implementation through periodic reviews, transaction audits, and management of non-halal funds that may arise.

The DPS uses various instruments such as standard policies and procedures, sharia risk registers, key risk indicators (KRIs), reporting channels, and whistleblowing mechanisms in its supervision of LKS. The standards referred to by the DPS include national fatwas, regulatory provisions, and international standards such as those of the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) and the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB). The integration of these standards aims to ensure consistency, transparency, and compatibility across jurisdictions. DPS is also expected to be able to translate the principles of Maqashid al-Shariah into concrete strategies, such as supporting financial inclusion, environmentally friendly financing, empowering women and vulnerable groups, and ensuring the trustworthy management of social funds.

Various studies show that the implementation of DPS functions in the field still faces significant challenges. One of the main issues is the lack of transparency and independence. The study Shah et al., (2023) "(Shah et al., 2023) reveals that the DPS decision-making process is often not fully transparent and tends to be influenced by relationships with LKS management, which can reduce the objectivity of supervision. This has an impact on public trust, as evidenced by the findings of Hidayat and Abduh (2020), which show that around 60% of customers still doubt the ability of the DPS to ensure sharia compliance. In addition, the capacity and competence of DPS members is another challenge that is no less important. Haniffa and Hudaib (2019) noted that many DPS members in Indonesia do not yet have adequate

certification or expertise in Islamic finance and risk management. As a result, the DPS faces difficulties in assessing modern financial product innovations, such as fintech, green sukuk, and Islamic derivative instruments.

Other research by (Mehmood et al., 2024 and Sudarwanto et al., 2024) confirms the gap between the ideal function of DPS and its implementation in the field. This gap is evident in several aspects, such as limited resources, lack of secretariat support, and weak harmonization of standards at the national and international levels. Challenges also arise from technological developments and digitalization, where DPS must be able to assess the sharia compliance of innovations such as smart contracts, electronic signatures, and fintech platforms. This requires updating competencies and a more adaptive supervisory approach.

The phenomenon of the gap between public expectations regarding sharia integrity and the reality on the ground is receiving increasing attention in the literature on Islamic finance. Essentially, the public and customers view the Sharia Supervisory Board (SSB) as the front line responsible for ensuring that all activities of Islamic Financial Institutions (IFIs) are conducted in accordance with sharia principles. These expectations extend beyond formal compliance with fatwas to include strict, independent, and transparent oversight, from product planning to operational implementation. Customers, investors, and other stakeholders view the integrity of the SSC as one of the main factors in assessing the credibility and sustainability of an institution, given that any violation of Sharia principles has implications not only for legal and financial aspects, but also for moral and reputational aspects.

Various studies and reports show that these expectations have not been fully met. There have been a number of cases of sharia violations in LKS operations, raising critical questions about the effectiveness of DPS supervision. Research on the (Alsaghir, 2023 dan Sudarwanto et al., 2024) highlights that there are still gaps in the supervisory mechanism that cause a mismatch between practice and the principles that should be upheld. These gaps can take the form of a lack of transparency in the decision-making process, potential conflicts of interest, and limitations in identifying and addressing sharia risks in a timely manner. This situation further reinforces the perception that the DPS is not yet functioning optimally as an independent supervisor, thereby raising public doubts about the institution's commitment to sharia values.

Services Board (IFSB). In its 2021 report, the IFSB noted that around 35% of customers in the Southeast Asian region, including Indonesia, expressed uncertainty regarding the sharia compliance of the LKS they use. This figure indicates a low level of confidence in the LKS's ability to consistently maintain sharia integrity. For financial institutions, this kind of distrust is a significant reputational risk, as trust is the main capital that supports business continuity. A decline in trust

can affect customer loyalty, hamper market growth, and even trigger systemic risk if it occurs on a widespread basis.

Other studies also confirm the serious implications of this condition. (Khalil, 2021; Rashid et al., 2022; Salami et al., 2024). reveal that negative perceptions of sharia management can lead to a decline in institutional competitiveness and hinder the development of new products. On the other hand, customer uncertainty about the integrity of institutions necessitates governance reforms and capacity building for DPS to better address the complexity of modern products, service digitalization, and global market dynamics. In other words, the gap between expectations and reality is not only a technical oversight issue but also a strategic aspect that determines the sustainability of institutions. Overall, this gap phenomenon demands a swift and comprehensive response. It requires regulatory strengthening, increased transparency in the supervisory process, the use of technology for real-time auditing and monitoring, and continuous training for DPS members so that they are able to carry out independent and credible supervisory functions. Only with such comprehensive measures can public trust be restored and the role of LKS as a trustworthy, competitive institution that complies with sharia principles be realized in practice.

Customer trust in sharia aspects is one of the main pillars that determine the success and sustainability of Sharia Financial Institutions (SFIs). In this context, trust is not only understood as customers' belief that the transactions and services they use are formally in accordance with Islamic principles, but also includes perceptions of integrity, transparency, and professionalism in the management of these institutions (Alaudin et al., 2015; Hasan et al., 2020; Mohd Noor, 2024) . When customers have full confidence in the sharia compliance of LKS, this will encourage higher loyalty, increase customer retention, and expand the basis of community participation in the sharia financial ecosystem. Conversely, if doubts or dissatisfaction arise regarding the oversight mechanisms and implementation of Sharia principles, this could lead to reputational risks, lower public trust, and potentially reduce the number of customers significantly.

Optimizing the function of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) is an urgent need that cannot be ignored. The DPS acts as the front line in ensuring that every product, service, and operational activity of LKS complies with applicable sharia provisions. This function includes issuing fatwas, operational supervision, sharia audits, and providing strategic recommendations for the development of innovative new products that remain in line with Islamic principles. This study considers that the extent to which the DPS performs its functions optimally will greatly influence customer perception and trust. Therefore, it is important to explore the extent to which this supervisory function has been carried out effectively, what obstacles have been encountered, and what factors influence the level of customer trust in Sharia aspects.

This study also aims to formulate strategies for optimizing the role of the DPS so that it can make a more significant contribution to strengthening sharia governance in LKS. These strategies may include improving the competence and certification of DPS members, implementing a technology-based monitoring system, and strengthening transparency and independence in the decision-making process. By integrating regulatory aspects, human resource capacity, and technology utilization, it is hoped that the DPS can perform its functions more effectively and adaptively to developments in the modern financial industry. Thus, the results of this study are expected to provide practical recommendations that not only increase customer trust but also strengthen the competitiveness of LKS in an increasingly competitive financial market, while maintaining consistent sharia integrity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sharia Compliance

Sharia Compliance is rooted in Islamic principles that emphasize integrity, transparency, and adherence to Sharia law in all aspects of life, including economic and financial activities (Cherni & Ben Amar, 2024; Sueb et al., 2022) . In the context of Sharia financial institutions (SFIs), Sharia compliance refers to the application of Islamic legal principles in all products, services, and financial operations. This aims to ensure that LKS activities are in line with Islamic ethical values, such as the prohibition of *riba* (interest), *gharar* (uncertainty), *maysir* (speculation), and activities involving the non-halal sector. This theory emphasizes the importance of *sharia governance*, which includes oversight structures, procedures, and evaluation mechanisms to ensure that all LKS activities comply with sharia principles. One of the key components of sharia governance is the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS), which is tasked with issuing fatwas, conducting oversight, and providing advice on the development of sharia financial products. According to this theory, the existence of the DPS is crucial to ensure customer trust and maintain the reputation of LKS. In its implementation, sharia compliance has a multidisciplinary dimension, involving legal, ethical, and economic aspects. Compliance with sharia principles not only provides spiritual benefits for customers, but also creates trust, loyalty, and operational sustainability for LKS. Non-compliance with sharia principles, on the other hand, can result in reputational risk, customer distrust, and potential sanctions from sharia authorities.

Transparency

The theory of transparency is an important concept in various disciplines, including economics, management, law, and politics, which emphasizes openness of information and accountability in decision-making, policy implementation, and organizational management (Ali et al., 2020; Cuadrado-Ballesteros & Bisogno, 2023; Mungiu-Pippidi, 2023) .

“Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from The Perspective of Maqashid Sharia”

Transparency can be defined as the ability of a party, whether an individual or an organization, to provide information that is accurate, complete, accessible, and understandable to interested parties. In the modern context, transparency is considered a key prerequisite for building trust, preventing corruption, and creating good *governance* (Uddin et al., 2024). Conceptually, transparency refers to openness in three main aspects: accessibility of information, clarity of processes, and sustainability of accountability. Accessibility of information includes the availability of relevant data and information to the public, enabling relevant parties to understand, verify, or evaluate actions taken by an entity. Clarity of process relates to efforts to make decision-making procedures and mechanisms easy to understand, as well as avoiding complexity that could lead to suspicion or distrust. Meanwhile, sustainability of accountability emphasizes that transparency must be followed by responsibility on the part of those who provide information for the results of their actions.

The theory of transparency in management literature is often associated with the *principal-agent* model (Odoch et al., 2022). This model explains how transparency helps reduce *information asymmetry* between *principals* (stakeholders, such as shareholders or the public) and *agents* (managers or executors) (Wang, 2021). Information asymmetry is often the main cause of corruption, manipulation, or unfairness in decision-making. With transparency, *principals* can monitor the actions of *agents* more effectively, thereby reducing the risk of abuse of power.

Transparency in organizations is also closely related to public trust. Transparent organizations tend to have a better reputation, as they provide assurance to the public that they operate with integrity and accountability. For example, in financial institutions, transparency in financial reporting and investment decision-making processes is important for building investor and customer trust. Normatively, transparency is also often associated with the concepts of justice, ethics, and participation. Transparency allows individuals or groups to participate in decision-making processes that affect them, while ensuring that decisions are made fairly and in accordance with ethical principles. Therefore, the theory of transparency is not only a technical framework, but also a moral foundation for creating a more inclusive and equitable system.

Fraud Theory

Fraud is an illegal act committed with the aim of obtaining unlawful gains, harming others, or manipulating information for specific purposes (Emara & Zhang, 2021; Sari & bin Mislan Cokrohadisumarto, 2019). In the context of organizations, both in the public and private sectors, fraud often involves abuse of authority, manipulation of financial reports, or breaches of integrity that damage reputation and disrupt sound governance. Fraud can take many forms, such

as corruption, embezzlement, document falsification, and violations of the principles of trust in relationships between parties. Fraud can cause significant material losses and destroy public trust in the institutions or organizations involved. Theoretically, one of the most well-known models for explaining the phenomenon of fraud is the Fraud Triangle, proposed by criminologist Donald Cressey (Din et al., 2022). This model states that fraud occurs when three key elements interact, namely pressure, opportunity, and rationalization. Pressure is a factor that drives individuals to commit fraud, such as personal financial pressure, unrealistic performance targets, or the need to maintain a certain lifestyle. Opportunity refers to situations where individuals have access to commit fraud without being detected, often due to weak internal control systems or loopholes in organizational procedures. Rationalization is the justification made by individuals who commit fraud to convince themselves that their actions are legitimate or acceptable, for example, by thinking that they are only "borrowing" money or assets from the organization that they consider insignificant.

Another more advanced theory is the Fraud Diamond (Bawekes et al., 2018), developed by David Wolfe and Dana Hermanson. The Fraud Diamond adds a fourth element, namely capability, which indicates that fraud can only be committed by individuals who have the skills, knowledge, or position that enable them to effectively abuse their power. This element clarifies that even though individuals are under pressure and have the opportunity to commit fraud, fraud only occurs if they have the capability to do so without being detected or prevented. In an organizational context, fraud can be divided into three main categories. First, *financial statement fraud*, which involves manipulating financial statements to give stakeholders a false impression, such as by overstating income or hiding liabilities. Second, *asset misappropriation*, which includes embezzlement or theft of company property and money. Third, *corruption*, which includes the abuse of authority for personal gain, such as bribery, extortion, or conflicts of interest (Cardao-Pito, 2023). These three types of fraud can have widespread adverse effects, both in the short and long term, on organizational stability and public trust.

Fraud prevention requires a comprehensive and systematic approach, which includes strengthening internal controls, implementing clear ethics in every line of the organization, and providing adequate training to detect signs of fraud. Internal and external audits also play an important role in identifying and preventing fraud. One of the main aspects of fraud prevention is creating a culture of transparency and accountability within the organization, where every decision and action can be clearly and openly accounted for. From the perspective of Maqashid Syariah, fraud contradicts the basic principles of Islam, which include justice, trustworthiness, and *maslahah*. Fraudulent acts damage individual integrity and harm society, contradicting the Sharia objectives of

“Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from The Perspective of Maqashid Sharia”

protecting property (*hifz al-mal*), life (*hifz al-nafs*), and honor (*hifz al-ird*). Therefore, the application of Sharia principles in organizational management systems can be an effective preventive approach in minimizing fraud practices, both in the public and private sectors. By ensuring compliance with the values of justice and transparency, it is hoped that fraud can be prevented, creating a safer, fairer, and more trustworthy environment for all parties involved.

Sharia Financial Institution

Sharia Financial Institutions (LKS) are institutions that operate based on Islamic sharia principles, which include prohibitions on usury, gharar (uncertainty), maysir (gambling), and activities that are unethical or contrary to Islamic teachings. Based on the theory of maqashid sharia, the main objective of LKS is to create *maslahah* (benefit) for the people by promoting economic justice, equitable welfare, and social sustainability (Anwer et al., 2020; Sani & Abubakar, 2020; Wajdi Dusuki, 2008). Within this framework, the operations of Islamic financial institutions do not only focus on achieving financial profits, but also on social values and sustainability. Islamic finance theory emphasizes three basic principles in the operations of Islamic financial institutions, namely: (1) based on *risk sharing* through contracts such as *mudharabah* (profit sharing) and *musyarakah* (investment cooperation); (2) avoiding interest-based transactions by replacing them with profit margin systems, leases, or *fees*; and (3) financial activities oriented towards the real sector to create economic added value (Ahmed, 2017; Mohammed et al., 2020). From a *sharia governance* perspective, Islamic financial institutions are designed to comply with sharia principles through a supervisory mechanism by the Sharia Supervisory Board (SSB), which is tasked with ensuring that all products, services, and operations of Islamic financial institutions are in accordance with Islamic law. This governance aims to maintain integrity and transparency, which are important for increasing customer trust and loyalty.

Sharia Supervisory Board

The Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) is a key component in the governance structure of Sharia Financial Institutions (LKS), tasked with ensuring that all operational activities, products, and services comply with the principles of Islamic finance. The existence of the DPS is based on the Sharia legal framework, which emphasizes the importance of integrity, transparency, and accountability in Islamic financial management. The theory of *sharia governance* places the DPS as a supervisory institution that has the functions of fatwa, audit, and consultation (Abdulrahman et al., 2024a; Ayub et al., 2023; Indrawaty & Wardayati, 2016). The fatwa function includes providing guidelines related to product development in accordance with Islamic law, while the audit function involves supervising the operational implementation of sharia in LKS activities (Bhatti, 2020; Sadr, 2014; Wajdi

Dusuki, 2008). In the context of customer loyalty, *trust theory* is relevant to explain how DPS influences customers' perceptions of the integrity and sharia compliance of LKS. When customers feel confident that the financial services they use are in line with Islamic values, their loyalty to LKS tends to increase (Majeed & Zainab, 2018; Sueb et al., 2022). In addition, *agency theory* highlights the importance of DPS independence to mitigate conflicts of interest between LKS management and customers (Can, 2021; Neifar et al., 2020; Sueb et al., 2022). The role of the DPS can be optimized through a competency-based approach, which emphasizes the importance of training and certification for DPS members so that they are able to understand modern financial dynamics without abandoning sharia principles.

Objectives of Sharia

Maqashid Syariah is an essential concept in Islamic law that aims to ensure that all laws and policies formulated based on sharia lead to the creation of benefits for humanity (Soleh, 2016; Supriyono et al., 2019). Maqashid Syariah, which means "the objectives of Sharia," serves as a framework for understanding the main purpose of applying Islamic law, which is to protect and fulfill human needs holistically. This concept was first developed by Imam Al-Juwaini and expanded in depth by scholars such as Imam Al-Ghazali and Imam Asy-Syatibi (Rahman et al., 2017; Rakhmadi et al., 2022). Broadly speaking, Maqashid Syariah encompasses five main objectives known as *kulliyat al-khams*, namely the protection of religion (*hifz al-din*), life (*hifz al-nafs*), intellect (*hifz al-aql*), lineage (*hifz al-nasl*), and property (*hifz al-mal*). Protection of religion (*hifz al-din*) aims to ensure the freedom of human beings to practice their religious teachings and prevent actions that could undermine their beliefs or faith. This principle is a fundamental pillar of Sharia law, as religion is a pillar of human life. Furthermore, protection of life (*hifz al-nafs*) emphasizes the importance of human safety and security. Sharia prohibits actions that threaten life, such as murder, violence, or anything else that endangers the lives of individuals and society. The principle of protection of reason (*hifz al-aql*) aims to ensure that humans can use their reason optimally in living their lives. Therefore, Sharia encourages education, training, and intellectual development, and prohibits things that can damage the intellect, such as alcohol or drug consumption. Protection of offspring (*hifz al-nasl*) focuses on preserving the institution of family and public morality. This principle supports legal marriage, prohibits adultery, and regulates harmonious family life. Finally, protection of property (*hifz al-mal*) ensures economic justice through proper resource management, protection of property rights, implementation of zakat, and prohibition of usury and corruption.

According to Imam Asy-Syatibi, Maqashid Syariah also has a hierarchy of needs divided into three levels: *dharuriyat* (basic needs), *hajiyyat* (complementary needs), and *tahsiniyat*

“Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from The Perspective of Maqashid Sharia”

(perfection needs) (Harahap et al., 2023; Kasim et al., 2021; Soleh, 2016). The *dharuriyat* level includes basic needs such as security, health, and economic stability that must be met to sustain human life. The *hajiyyat* level supports complementary needs that improve the comfort of life, such as infrastructure and public services. Meanwhile, the *tahsiniyat* level focuses on perfecting and improving the quality of life through aesthetics, innovation, and beauty.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with the aim of analyzing the role of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in ensuring sharia compliance and transparency as an effort to prevent fraud in Sharia Financial Institutions (LKS) from the perspective of Maqashid Sharia. This approach was chosen because it allows researchers to gain an in-depth understanding of Sharia supervision practices, institutional dynamics, and the normative values that underlie Sharia financial governance.

The research data was obtained through a combination of literature studies and field studies. The literature study was conducted by reviewing scientific journals, reference books, sharia governance standards, and relevant regulations to develop a conceptual framework for the research. Meanwhile, empirical data was collected through in-depth interviews with purposively selected informants, consisting of DPS members, LKS management, and parties with expertise in sharia supervision and compliance. Data collection was also supported by a documentation study of sharia compliance reports and related institutional documents.

Data analysis was conducted thematically through a process of reduction, grouping, and interpretation of data, linking empirical findings to the principles of Maqashid Sharia, particularly the protection of property and the prevention of harm. Data validity was maintained through triangulation of sources and methods to ensure the consistency and credibility of the research results.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on in-depth interviews conducted with several key informants, a comprehensive picture was obtained regarding the role of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in realizing sharia compliance and transparency, as well as fraud prevention strategies through the Maqashid Sharia approach. The informants consisted of DPS members, compliance officers, internal auditors of sharia financial institutions, and academics competent in the field of sharia finance. One of the DPS members (Informant 1) emphasized that the main role of the DPS is not only to check the conformity of products and transactions with DSN-MUI fatwas, but also to ensure that all business processes reflect maqashid values. He said: *"We strive to ensure that every decision and product that comes out of this institution not only complies with the text of the fatwa, but also fulfills its spirit, which is to bring benefit and*

prevent harm. If the process is transparent from the outset, the risk of fraud can be reduced." This statement shows that the DPS does not only perform a formalistic function, but also a preventive one by building a system that closes opportunities for violations.

A similar view was expressed by a compliance manager who said that the implementation of *sharia compliance* is closely related to reporting integrity and information disclosure. According to him: *"Transparency is not only about neat annual reports, but also how every transaction can be clearly traced, and the DPS has full access to check it at any time. We are aware that fraud often occurs not only because of intent, but also because there are loopholes that are not monitored."* This indicates that optimizing the role of DPS requires a real-time reporting system that enables continuous monitoring. On the other hand, an internal auditor highlighted the challenges faced by DPS, especially in dealing with the complexity of modern sharia financial products. He explained: *"Products such as hybrid sukuk or fintech-based financing have complex structures. If the DPS does not fully understand the scheme, the potential for abuse is very high. That is why continuing education for the DPS is very important."* This quote underscores the need to increase the capacity of the DPS so that it can keep up with the development of Islamic financial instruments that are increasingly innovative but risky.

The academic perspective reinforces this finding by emphasizing that the Maqashid Shariah approach can serve as a strategic guide for the DPS. He states: *"If the DPS truly understands maqashid, then supervision does not stop at the legal aspect alone, but also assesses whether a transaction brings benefits or has the potential to harm certain parties. The principle of dar'ul mafasid must be the main guideline."* This is in line with the principle of preventing harm, which is at the core of maqashid and is relevant to building an effective anti-fraud system of . The interview results also show that several DPS have integrated the *Sharia Maqashid Index* into the institutional performance evaluation process. A senior DPS (Informant 5) said: *"We use maqashid indicators to assess the extent to which this institution not only makes a financial profit but also contributes socially. If there are practices that are profitable for the business but harmful to society, we correct them."* This practice broadens the scope of DPS supervision so that it is not merely pursuing administrative compliance, but also moral and social sustainability.

All informants agreed that optimizing the role of DPS still faces obstacles. Factors such as the limited number of competent DPS, potential conflicts of interest with management, resistance to transparency, and low sharia literacy among the public are challenges that require long-term solutions. Several informants suggested increasing synergy between the DPS, regulators, and external auditors,

“Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from The Perspective of Maqashid Sharia”

as well as utilizing information technology to build a secure, fast, and accurate reporting system.

Analysis of the Role of DPS in Maintaining Sharia Compliance

The results of this study indicate that the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) plays a very strategic role in ensuring *sharia compliance* in Islamic financial institutions. Findings from interviews with informants show that the DPS functions not only as an administrative supervisor but also as a management advisor and guardian of sharia maqashid values. This is in line with the concept of *Sharia governance* described by Archer and Karim (2007), which emphasizes that the DPS is the main pillar of Sharia governance that has moral, legal, and institutional authority in maintaining the Sharia compliance of financial institutions. Confirmation of this theory can be seen in practice in the field, where informants emphasize that the involvement of the DPS from the product planning stage to post-launch evaluation is a form of preventive and curative supervision, thereby minimizing the potential for violations of sharia principles.

Empirically, the findings of this study are consistent with the study conducted by Rahman and Bukair (2015), which shows that the existence of an active and competent DPS can improve the quality of sharia supervision and strengthen the legitimacy of sharia financial institutions in the eyes of the public. In the Indonesian context, Setiawan's (2020) research also found that DPS that carry out intensive supervisory functions contribute to increased customer trust and consumer loyalty, because the public sees a guarantee of sharia compliance in the products offered. This is reinforced by the data from this study, in which informants from the DPS emphasized the importance of their involvement from the early stages of product design, so that potential violations such as *riba*, *gharar*, or *maysir* can be anticipated before the product is launched. Thus, it can be concluded that the supervisory function of the DPS is not only reactive to violations, but proactive in ensuring that every product and transaction complies with DSN-MUI fatwas and applicable regulations.

This study also confirms the dual role of DPS as an independent supervisor and management advisor. From the perspective of sharia governance theory, this dual role is referred to as a *supervisory* and *advisory* function (Ginena & Hamid, 2015). The supervisory function is manifested through periodic sharia audits as revealed by internal auditor informants, while the advisory function is reflected in the DPS's involvement in providing recommendations related to product innovations that do not yet have specific fatwas. Empirically, this is in line with Grassa's (2013) research, which found that DPS in various countries, including Indonesia and Malaysia, often play an active role in providing practical solutions to the dynamics of Islamic financial products, especially when dealing with complex innovations.

Field confirmation from this study shows that the DPS not only emphasizes legal-formal aspects, but also prioritizes the values of sharia maqashid, namely maintaining *maslahah* and avoiding *mudarat* in financial transactions.

The *reporting function* carried out by DPS as found in this study also strengthens the dimensions of transparency and accountability. Periodic reports prepared by DPS and submitted to management, the Board of Commissioners, DSN-MUI, and regulators such as OJK are important mechanisms in creating clarity of public information. This is in line with the *accountability framework* theory in *Islamic corporate governance* described by Chapra and Ahmed (2002), which states that transparency and accountability are crucial elements in ensuring that Islamic financial institutions do not deviate from the principles of sharia. Empirically, these findings are in line with Hasan's (2011) research, which shows that DPS reports have a significant influence on the level of trust of stakeholders, both customers and regulators, because these reports are a clear indicator of sharia compliance practices.

The *maqashid shariah* perspective on the role of DPS in this study also confirms its importance as an instrument in realizing protection for the five main objectives of shariah, particularly *hifdz al-mal* (protection of property) and *hifdz al-din* (protection of religion). DPS not only ensures the absence of usury, *gharar*, and *maysir* practices, but also prevents Islamic financial institutions from engaging in fraud or manipulation that harms customers and undermines public trust. This confirmation is in line with Ayub's (2019) research, which emphasizes that DPS has an important role in maintaining the integrity of the sharia financial system so that it remains in line with the principles of *maslahah* and justice. In this study, the statement by informant 4, which asserts that the orientation of Islamic financial institutions should not be solely profit-oriented but rather *maslahah*-oriented, is clear evidence that the *maqashid shariah* perspective has been used as the basis for DPS supervision.

The results of this study reinforce the theory of *shariah governance*, which places the DPS as a central actor in maintaining shariah compliance, confirms previous empirical findings regarding the contribution of the DPS to legitimacy and public trust, and confirms field data showing that the DPS in Indonesia has performed its supervisory, advisory, fatwa, and reporting functions relatively effectively. However, this study also highlights challenges in terms of consistency of implementation, DPS competence, and limited coordination with management. This implies that optimizing the role of the DPS still requires strengthening its capacity, independence, and integrity in order to truly realize full sharia compliance and transparency, while also functioning as a bulwark against fraud from the perspective of maqashid sharia.

The Challenges Facing the DPS in Achieving Transparency and Preventing Fraud

The challenges faced by the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in ensuring transparency and preventing fraud in Islamic financial institutions can be confirmed through the theory of *sharia governance* and empirical findings from various previous studies. Theoretically, *the Sharia Governance Framework* (IFSB, 2009) emphasizes that the role of the DPS is not limited to issuing fatwas, but also includes performing effective oversight of risk management, compliance, and information transparency. The complexity of modern Islamic financial products such as hybrid sukuk, sharia-based derivatives, and fintech services, as revealed in the interviews, is in line with the study by Archer & Karim (2007), which shows that the more innovative Islamic products are, the higher the risk of *grey areas* in sharia that can be exploited as loopholes for fraud. This finding reinforces the *agency* theory perspective, which states that the more complex the structure of contracts and financial instruments, the greater the potential for *information asymmetry* between management, the DPS, and customers, thus requiring greater oversight capacity.

From a regulatory perspective, the obstacles to harmonizing reporting standards revealed by informants are consistent with the study by Farook et al. (2011), which confirms that differences between national regulations and international standards such as AAOIFI and IFSB can lead to inconsistencies in supervision. Empirical data from OJK (2022) shows that there is still a significant gap between the sharia compliance reports prepared by LKS and international sharia accounting standards, making it difficult to conduct a comprehensive sharia audit. This condition supports the argument of Haniffa & Hudaib (2007) that non-transparent reporting can weaken accountability and increase the risk of hidden fraud.

The limitations in the competence and capacity of DPS identified in field research are also confirmed by the findings of Hasan (2011), who states that many DPS in Southeast Asia are still appointed based on social or religious reputation, rather than solely on technical expertise. As a result, their supervisory functions are often normative and unable to anticipate complex technical risks. An empirical study by Bank Indonesia (2019) even found that only about 47% of DPS have a dual background (fiqh muamalah and finance), whereas ideally multidisciplinary expertise is needed to oversee modern instruments such as *blockchain-based* financing or digital assets. This reinforces the *resource-based view* theory, which emphasizes the importance of human resource competence in ensuring governance excellence.

The potential for conflicts of interest between the DPS and management that emerged in the interview findings is also in line with Grassa's (2013) research, which confirms that the independence of the DPS is often compromised due to economic dependence on the institutions it supervises. This

conflict of interest makes DPS reluctant to disclose irregularities that could potentially damage the institution's reputation. Data from the Islamic Finance Development Report (IFSB, 2021) notes that 22% of cases of sharia compliance violations in global Islamic banking are related to weak DPS independence and limited supervisory authority. *Institutional governance* theory asserts that the independence of supervisors is a prerequisite for effective governance, because without autonomy in decision-making, the supervisory function is merely symbolic (*ceremonial compliance*).

Internal resistance to transparency revealed by informants is consistent with the study by Maali et al. (2006), which found that many Islamic banks are reluctant to disclose detailed data related to business practices on the grounds of confidentiality, even though transparency is an important factor in building public trust. The lack of public literacy regarding Islamic finance also exacerbates this condition. Ascarya's (2020) empirical study shows that the public's low understanding of Islamic products has implications for weak external social control over Islamic financial institutions, so that supervision depends solely on the DPS.

The challenges of monitoring digital transactions and application-based fraud as revealed by informants are in line with the PwC (2022) report, which confirms that *cyber fraud* in Islamic financial institutions has increased significantly with the adoption of fintech. Without *regtech* capabilities and *real-time monitoring*, DPS risks being unable to detect data manipulation or illegal transactions. Further empirical confirmation can be found in the research by Rahman & Bukair (2015), which states that *the use of machine learning and blockchain-based regulatory technology* (RegTech) can increase the effectiveness of sharia auditing by up to 35% in detecting transaction anomalies.

These research findings do not stand alone, but are confirmed by sharia governance theory, empirical data from regulators, and previous research results. Product complexity, regulatory disharmony, limitations in DPS competence, conflicts of interest, resistance to transparency, technological risks, and low public literacy have proven to be universal challenges faced by DPS in a global context. The recommended mitigation efforts, such as increasing DPS capacity, utilizing regtech, harmonizing reporting standards, strengthening independence, and improving public literacy, are in line with sharia maqashid, particularly *hifzh al-mal* (protection of property) and *dar'ul mafasid* (prevention of harm). By placing the principles of maqashid as the foundation, the technical strategy for strengthening DPS is not only oriented towards formal compliance, but also towards achieving the ethical and social sustainability of Islamic financial institutions.

The Maqashid Shariah Approach in Optimizing the Role of DPS

The Maqashid Syariah approach as a normative framework has strategic relevance in strengthening the role of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in preventing fraud and increasing transparency in Islamic financial institutions. Theoretically, Maqashid Syariah, as formulated by al-Ghazali and al-Shatibi, emphasizes the protection of five main aspects: religion, life, intellect, lineage, and property. In the context of finance, the principle of *hifzh al-mal* (protection of wealth) is the fundamental basis for preventing losses due to fraud and irregularities, while the principle of *dar' al-mafasid wa jalb al-masalih* (preventing harm and bringing benefit) directs institutions to ensure that every financial activity brings value. This perspective is reinforced by the theory of *Islamic Corporate Governance*, which places Maqashid Shariah as the ultimate goal of DPS supervision, so that supervision is not limited to *rule compliance* but also *value compliance*. This confirms the opinion of Chapra and Ahmed (2002), who emphasize that sharia governance must be oriented towards justice, transparency, and the protection of stakeholder rights in accordance with maqashid.

Research findings show that DPS needs to focus on fraud prevention through proactive mechanisms in line with the research by Antonio et al. (2012), which states that integrating maqashid into the supervisory framework can improve the effectiveness of internal sharia audit functions. The principle of *dar'ul mafasid*, for example, has proven to be relevant in establishing an internal control system capable of detecting early indications of fraud. Empirical data from the Financial Services Authority (OJK, 2021) also shows that Islamic banks that integrate maqashid into their governance policies have higher levels of sharia compliance disclosure than those that are only oriented towards formal regulatory compliance. This supports Asutay's (2012) argument that the success of Islamic institutions should be measured not only by profitability, but also by the achievement of maqashid objectives, including justice, social welfare, and institutional integrity.

Empirical literature also shows how maqashid can serve as an objective benchmark for DPS. A study by Mohammed et al. (2015) through the development of *the Maqashid Shariah Index (MSI)* shows that Islamic financial institutions that are oriented towards maqashid have better social performance and transparency levels, as well as lower fraud incidence rates. These findings are consistent with the interview results, which mention that the use of the Maqashid Index can be a guideline for a more comprehensive evaluation of sharia compliance. In addition, Ascarya's (2020) research confirms that sharia maqashid literacy among DPS contributes significantly to strengthening ethics-based governance, so that fraud prevention is not only carried out through technical mechanisms, but also through moral-spiritual strengthening.

The importance of internalizing moral and ethical values as an instrument for fraud prevention, as revealed by informants, is supported by *Ethical Governance* theory, which emphasizes the integration of formal compliance and individual ethical awareness. Empirically, the study by Haniffa & Hudaib (2007) shows that Islamic banks that prioritize ethical values and trustworthiness in internal supervision are able to increase public trust and strengthen the transparency of financial reports. This is also in line with Khan's (2013) research, which emphasizes that the integration of maqashid into organizational culture encourages the creation of *an Islamic work ethic*, which has been proven to reduce the risk of employee misconduct, including fraudulent practices.

Thus, field findings showing that DPS uses maqashid as a reference in supervision have a strong theoretical and empirical basis. Maqashid Sharia provides a framework that emphasizes a balance between formal compliance, moral integrity, and the achievement of *maslahah*, so that the supervisory function is not merely administrative, but also transformational. The integration of maqashid into DPS strategies not only prevents fraud and increases transparency, but also strengthens the social and spiritual legitimacy of Islamic financial institutions. Ultimately, the application of maqashid makes DPS a pillar of Sharia governance that safeguards trust, protects the interests of the community, and ensures the sustainability of institutions in accordance with Islamic values.

5. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) plays a very strategic role in ensuring sharia compliance in Islamic financial institutions. This role includes supervisory functions, providing advice, and issuing fatwas on the products and operations of the institution, which are not only oriented towards formal compliance with DSN-MUI fatwas and laws and regulations, but also towards maintaining integrity, ethics, and fairness in business activities. Through the perspective of Maqashid Syariah, the DPS acts as a moral guardian that ensures every transaction and policy brings benefits and prevents harm, while also strengthening transparency and fraud prevention efforts. However, this study has several limitations, namely its exploratory nature as it is based on literature and limited interviews, it does not integrate quantitative analysis of the effectiveness of fraud prevention, and it does not fully capture the variations in the implementation of the DPS role in various types of institutions such as BUS, BPRS, and LKMS. However, this study has important implications in academic, practical, and policy terms. Academically, the results enrich the discourse on Islamic financial governance by emphasizing the relevance of Maqashid Syariah as a normative and operational framework for strengthening the role of DPS. Practically, these findings emphasize the need to

increase the capacity of DPS members through continuous training, the use of technology in the supervisory system, and the improvement of Islamic finance literacy among the public. From a policy perspective, this study provides input for regulators such as the OJK and DSN-MUI to develop Islamic supervisory guidelines that are more adaptive to the complexities of the modern Islamic finance industry. Considering the existing limitations, further research is recommended to combine qualitative and quantitative methods, expand the scope of respondents, and conduct comparative studies between types of Islamic financial institutions to produce a more comprehensive and applicable understanding of optimizing the role of DPS in strengthening sharia compliance, transparency, and fraud prevention.

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“Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from The Perspective of Maqashid Sharia”

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“Optimizing the Role of The Sharia Supervisory Board in Realizing Sharia Compliance and Transparency: Fraud Prevention Efforts from The Perspective of Maqashid Sharia”

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